
Management and Business Research Quarterly

2020(13)1–14

Linking Corporate Culture Values and Organizational Agility: An Empirical Analysis within the Automotive Industry

Lisa-Marie Ahl

Universidad Católica San Antonio de Murcia, UCAM International Ph.D. School (EIDUCAM), Spain

Received 04 January 2020

Accepted 2 February 2020

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to analyze the link of corporate values with respect to the concept of organizational agility. The motivation has been one of discovery within corporations from the automotive industry, dealing in uncertain and turbulent environments. The paper offers an overview of literature on agility frameworks, comparing overlapping areas of corporate values from the 10 largest premium automotive manufacturers. Survey data from over 186 respondents provide quantitative validity to establish understanding of how organizational agility is translated into values and behaviors. A conceptual framework for synthesizing the relationships is proposed based on the case studies' empirical findings. As a result, organizations can benefit from its development in two ways: (1) it helps measuring the agility-values fit with an integrative perspective, and (2) it provides valuable insights into critical elements of their organizational culture. Moreover, a wide range of values under theoretical and practical situations is proposed. This study will enable executives, especially from the automotive industry, to identify suitable characteristics that would simultaneously improve an organization's agile performance by considering aspects of corporate culture. Consequently, this study is more industry-specific and less inclusive.

Keywords: *Corporate Values, Organizational Culture, Change Management, Workforce Agility, Organizational Ethics*

Introduction

Economic success in today's fast-changing, highly competitive environment demands dynamic capabilities for change and flexibility. In this context, knowing specific mechanisms for adopting agile business practices means to stay ahead while survive crisis. The managerial enthusiasm which

Corresponding author. E-mail address: lisa-marie.ahl1@fom-net.de

Doi:10.32038/mbrq.2020.13.01

has grown the concept of organizational agility comes up with certain source of ambiguity (Charbonnier-Voirin, 2011). Over the last years, the technological-driven focus of many businesses has led to overlooking contextual organizational soft-factors, such as culture, communication and leadership behavior (Felipe, Roldán, & Leal-Rodríguez, 2016).

Due to that fact, system and cultural fundamentals that support agile frameworks in the 21st Century are scarce in a lot of companies. Especially the automotive industry is well known for entering a new era, driven by changing business models and amended value chains. Several technological developments currently have the potential to substantially transform this type of industry branch (Bardt, 2017). In this vein, the hardest part of successful leading an organizational transformation is the cultural mindset with strong values that shape a corporate's identity. It will either support the new state of art or block it while facing the problem of employees not evolving to corporate change. This paper therefore sheds light on the organization's human talent and its clear actions to shift cultural values and expectations. The research gap of prior scholarly work will be empirically analyzed using a two-stage approach. Firstly, a cluster of corporate values from the 10 largest premium automotive manufacturers in comparison to agile attitudes and beliefs from different studies will be enclosed. Secondly, the conceptual model proposed will serve not only for explanatory purposes, but also for empirical evidence, testing its validity through a quantitative pre-study. This work consequently means to answer the following question: What are the links between corporate values and the concept of organizational agility?

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. Section 2 provides the theoretical background for the study in terms of organizational agility and corporate culture values. The third section describes the methodological procedure as well as data collection process. The results of the different data analyses are presented and discussed in the fourth section. Finally, Section 5 and 6 bring together the practical contributions, limitations, and avenues for future research work.

Literature and theoretical underpinnings

Existing frameworks for organizational agility

The concept of agility has been the topic of increasing research interest, both in academic and practical view, during the last two decades introduced in 1991 (Rahman, 2014). Combining a practical background, especially American corporations from the information technology sector had adopted the concept of corporate agility in the mid-1990s. Based on a comprehensive literature review from top management journals, several definitions for organizational agility have been proposed so far, varying in certain perspectives. The concept has been initially introduced as a manufacturing system with extraordinary capabilities, also referred to as "dynamic capabilities", which provide organizations the potency to promptly respond to the market changes by reconfiguring its processes, strategies, and resources (Felipe et al., 2016). The dynamic capability-building process include elements of ambidexterity such as organizational resiliencies in terms of adaptation, flexibility, and agility that constitute main drivers for innovativeness (Lee & Rha, 2016). This study suggests the concept of organizational agility as a latent and multidimensional construct based on a combination of resilience and innovativeness, because agility meets the requirements of ambidexterity.

Related scholarly work can be mainly divided into two areas: the first group concentrates on adaptive agile attributes that explore agile organizational designs, whereas the second group include proactive agile practices to comply with organizational performance (Grantham, Ware, & Williamson, 2007; Sherehiy, Karwowski, & Layer, 2007; Appelbaum, Calla, Desautels, & Hasan, 2017). Hamel (2012) suggested that organizations should be built around people, meeting human needs and values to leverage their full innovation and creativity potential. In order to contribute to the development of organizational agility, an Organizational Agile Survey from 2018 identifies 48 behavioral practices that are characteristics of adaptive companies' culture and summarizes them into eight groups of principles: Commitment, Creating Value, Initiative, Support for Change, Leadership, Learning, Openness, and Respect and Challenge (Persona GLOBAL, 2018). All these attributes are key elements of successful employee involvement regarding organizational change. Indeed, such factors may interact with the capabilities comprising the 5S organizational agility framework according to Baškarada and Koronios (2018). The fragmented nature of the relevant research points to a lack of consensus as to which individual levers generate the necessary cohesion for transformation processes.

Consequently, the theoretical framework needs to be attentive towards the social dimension of the agile organization requiring a modification in aspirations and behaviors. This gap in the literature with respect to organizational agility goes far beyond the process level, into the psyche of the people embedding the corporate DNA. Consistent with existing research on agility at the organizational level, this study therefore sheds light on agility at the individual level given attention on how to develop agile capabilities (Braun, Hayes, DeMuth, & Taran, 2017).

The relationship between values and individual behavior

When investigating social processes, several researchers focusing on individual behavior instead of practices, enabling a better understanding of what happens within an organization. In this regard, sociological conceptions of culture particularly link intrinsic values that underpin organization members' activities and their goal achievement (Dempsey, 2015). Schein (2004) identified three distinct levels in organizational cultures, namely artifacts and behaviors, espoused values and basic underlying assumptions. In line with this distinction, corporate culture reflects an organization's personality consisting of taken-for-granted values guiding the "selection and evaluation of behaviors and events" (Illes & Vogell, 2018, p. 353). The definition implies a rational learning process through values as cognitive structures that motivate action.

Nonetheless, cultural change seems to be one of the major hurdles impeding organization's success. The "2018 Deloitte Global Human Capital Trends" found that although 94% of respondents believe that "agility and collaboration" are critical for the future-orientation of the firm, only 17% of people will actively endorse change (Deloitte Insights, 2018). According to Illes and Vogell (2018), corporate values are often designed by top management regardless of the values attractive to their employees. Therefore, employees perceive values and norms quite different at the individual level. The result will be an effect of social pressure, which leads to the following of norms through "espoused values", whereby employees loose motivating qualities and personal

identification. The implications of this insight are profound. In practice, it means that people are likely to be resistant to change. The need for a change in personal values requires a constant internally motivated adjustment endorsed by the social environment (Bardi, Lee, Hofmann-Towfigh, & Soutar, 2009). In this regard, research in the field of neuroscience has added the aspect of social connectedness as a key factor for individual identification with corporate values. Value change and identification might result from the wish to conform to a group forced by emotional experiences of social exclusion that create neural reactions as strong as physical pain (Ruff & Fehr, 2014).

In contrast to perceived values at a personal level, an agile group culture with its norms is mainly concerned with human relations, flexibility, and innovativeness. A firm's innovative culture involves dimensions like entrepreneurship, risk taking, and openness to new ideas (Schein, 2004). Trust and participation belonging to its core values, ensuring the smooth functioning of a group (Rahman, 2014; Schwartz et al., 2012). Despite large individual research on agility and corporate values, researchers have rarely examined the application of the two concepts and their underlying effects in the same study. Scholarly work on agility frameworks mainly address customer issues from business point of view, neglecting an inclusive approach of how employees relate to these values and objectives within corporations that do not seem to be at ease with organizational change.

Research methodology and data collection

Qualitative origins

Methodology used in this research is a mixture of qualitative and quantitative methods within one specific industry. The automotive industry with a particular focus on premium car manufacturers as an object of research is chosen, due to the fact that both academics and practitioners classify this type of industry as hypercompetitive in volatile and uncertain market conditions, while requiring flexibility to change of long-established corporations. The list of companies has been extracted from Arthur D. Little's viewpoint 'Battle for Sales in the Premium Segment' (2014) in combination with the Automotive INNOVATIONS study from 2018. The parameters taken into consideration include a combination of automobiles available for purchase on the market nowadays, together with an understanding of how many new automobiles the various premium manufacturer sell within an average price range of well-established 50,000 – 100,000 EUR per car. Nonetheless, no exact price figure has been the key factor, but rather an overall perception of the overall innovation power (Center of Automotive Management, 2018). In total, 562 innovations were identified from 32 premium automotive manufacturers. Consequently, the 10 most innovative premium car manufacturer based on total number of innovations were selected, as this is the most commonly used measure of innovation strength and future brand success. Not surprisingly, more than the half of selected corporations are headquartered in European countries: Germany (4), the U.S. (2), the UK (1), Sweden (1), China (1) and Japan (1). For an overview of the sample, see Table 1.

Based on a secondary data analysis, corporate value statements from the premium car manufacturers' corporate websites were collected at the end of April 2019. Thus, the 2019 corporate value statements of the 10 largest premium car manufacturers have been taken into consideration for the further cluster analysis. This level of cluster initiative is sociologically rooted to the building

of a collective group identity (Lis & Lis, 2016). Additionally, online sources or the case studies provided by advisory firms or consultants in management science and practices were used for information gathering on agility and behavior. The objective of this qualitative phase is to clarify the theoretical construct by exploring a set of items for evaluating the frequency of corporate values which typify organizational agility. In this regard, the main goal is to distill patterns in the relation between corporate values and organizational agility, using MAXQDA Analytics Pro version 18.0.1 as qualitative data analysis software. Documents were coded, key concepts were mapped, and analysis memos were written to elucidate key themes. In a further step, it will be useful to gain empirical quantitative evidence concerning the internal corporate perception of values and behavior.

Table 1. Sample overview, including sales volume, and total number of innovations in 2018.

<i>Premium automotive manufacturer</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Sales volume (in mio.)</i>	<i>Total innovations</i>
BMW GROUP	<i>Germany</i>	2,49	60
DAIMLER	<i>Germany</i>	2,31	63
AUDI	<i>Germany</i>	1,81	60
VOLVO	<i>Sweden</i>	0,64	24
LEXUS (TOYOTA)	<i>Japan</i>	0,58	35
JAGUAR LAND ROVER	<i>UK</i>	0,57	20
CADILLAC	<i>U.S.</i>	0,36	10
PORSCHE	<i>Germany</i>	0,25	24
TESLA	<i>U.S.</i>	0,24	24
NIO	<i>China</i>	0,01	40

Quantitative origins

In a second step, the applied method of quantitative data collection procedure used a survey design and therefore moves from theory to data in order to gain empirical evidence for the conceptual framework of the initial qualitative analysis. It was created bilingual through the online tool “SoSci Survey”, mainly with closed-ended questions in two dimensions that included a total set of 15 items and four control items. In order to operationalize the construct, the general multidimensional measures of innovativeness and resilience were adopted, as they are particularly relevant for leveraging the organizational climate regarding agility (Shoham, Vigoda-Gadot, Ruvio, & Schwabsky, 2012; Ruvio, Shoham, Vigoda-Gadot, & Schwabsky, 2014; Braun et al., 2017; Ali, Sun, & Ali, 2017).

The questionnaire uses 5-point Likert scale, ranging from one denoted as strongly disagree to five denoted as strongly agree. All answers were collected simultaneously over a two-month period in the last quarter of 2018, resulting in a final sample of completed questionnaires of about 186. Non-response bias was not a concern, as only two cases had to be excluded from the sample. Respondents should work for an automotive car manufacturer independent of location with different positions both at management and employee level, e.g. Executive, Consultant, or Specialist. These people were identified as capable and knowledgeable enough to complete the survey questionnaire by evaluating the perception of values, innovativeness, and corporate behavior in uncertain times.

In summary, the data analysis was conducted in four steps using descriptive statistics in R and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach.

Foremost, corporate value statements of the sample premium automotive manufacturer were investigated to find similarities and differences. For this purpose, the statements were clustered in six overarching groups. In a next step, the concept of organizational agility, measured by six items, was divided into characteristic change management traits of innovativeness (six items) and resilience (four items). Finally, the development of the conceptual framework helped to establish a link between certain corporate value statements and dimensions of organizational agility.

Results and discussions

Cluster of corporate values

The qualitative analysis of the corporate value statements from the 10 largest premium automotive manufacturers indicated a diverse set of values, beliefs, and codes of conduct. In fact, values are not independent units and often show overlapping areas. Consequently, the single cluster of values is further articulated and explained through other key words used by the corporation (i.e. if a company describes the value “Trust” with other words like “Honesty,” “Ethics,” “Integrity,” etc., all these words are grouped to one category). This procedure goes in line with scholarly work on existing scales for the measurement of corporate values (Rawlins, 2008; van Rekom, van Riel, & Wierenga, 2006; Abbott, White, & Charles, 2005). All values have been categorized in six overarching groups, providing corporate examples according to their frequency (see Table 2). This process induced the reduction of a broad list of values to a few categories strengthened by distinctive group dimensions, as revealed by the data. The cluster can be divided into: (1) Trust, (2) Responsibility, (3) Openness, (4) Appreciation, (5) Pioneering, and (6) Challenge.

Table 2. The six overarching groups of corporate values with corporate examples.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Group dimension</i>	<i>Company</i>
(1) trust	<i>Integrity, Honesty, Fairness, Transparency</i>	<i>BMW, Audi, Cadillac, Daimler, Porsche, Volvo,</i>
(2) responsibility	<i>Commitment, Supportive Environment, Safety, Care, Think Like Owners</i>	<i>BMW, Audi, Cadillac, Jaguar Land Rover, NIO, Tesla</i>
(3) openness	<i>Creativity, Enthusiasm, Spirit, Constantly Innovate, Do the Impossible, Teamwork</i>	<i>Tesla, Porsche, Daimler, Lexus</i>
(4) appreciation	<i>Respect, Unity, Diversity</i>	<i>Jaguar Land Rover, Porsche, BMW, Audi, Daimler</i>
(5) pioneering	<i>Passion, Courage, Entrepreneurship, Customer Success</i>	<i>Jaguar Land Rover, Porsche, Tesla, Volvo</i>
(6) challenge	<i>Change, Action, Vision, Move Fast, Reason from “First Principles”</i>	<i>NIO, Tesla, Lexus, Volvo</i>

At the core of most value statements lies a focus on integrity and trust (Zwetsloot, Scheppingen, Bos, Dijkman, & Starren, 2013). According to several researchers, integrity refers to the ethical behavior of doing the right thing, even when no one is watching (Abbott et al., 2005; Rawlins, 2008). Especially European premium automotive manufacturer-built trust-based organization-public relationships stimulating that all “activities are in harmony with the environment and society” (Daimler AG, 2019). The main goal is being transparent through the acknowledgement of

concerns (BMW Group, 2019) by offering clear and truthful information as well as acting in a disciplined (Daimler AG, 2019) and honest (Porsche AG, 2019) manner. The second value cluster is characterized by responsibility that refers to actions planned or undertaken and their corporate commitment (De Brentani & Kleinschmidt, 2004). It constitutes an important aspect of decision-making processes and opens space for taking ownerships of actions (Cadillac, 2019).

Another important value for premium automotive manufacturer refers to openness. This value is concerned with the spirit to take on new possibilities, encouraging “outside-the-box” thinking. It fosters an open-minded and knowledge-sharing culture with high level of collaboration and teamwork opportunities (Toyota Motor Corporation, 2019). In particular, new entrants are leveraged to an “influential entity in prompting radical ideas” (Meyer, 2019). The fourth value cluster is characterized by a positive attitude toward the social principle of appreciation. This category emphasizes a wider social interest in terms of respect, unity, and diversity. Organizations indicate actions like stakeholder dialogues, clear feedback as well as recognition (BMW Group, 2019).

Next, five out of ten premium automotive manufacturer mentioned values related to the pioneering passion of entrepreneurs. This fifth value cluster is mainly focused on “customer insights to develop innovative solutions” (Jaguar Land Rover, 2019), also based on courage and risk-taking behavior (Porsche AG, 2019). Sixth and final, taking on challenges adhere to the vision of sustainable companies that actively incorporate “change and transformation as a source of inspiration and energy” (Volvo Group, 2019). This value highly facilitates business resilience through responses in a speedy manner, but also constitutes a major source of failure. Curiosity, fast movements, and the ability to create new solutions from scratch are the cluster characteristic traits that are often addressed from automotive newcomers like Tesla (Meyer, 2019) or NIO (2019).

Relation between corporate values and agility

The findings across the automotive industry are supported by Talwar’s (2009) “Core values investigation of excellence models vis-à-vis human values”. Especially business excellence models from the U.S. (MBNQA) and Japan (JQA and Deming Prize) state agility, cooperation and organizational learning as important core values. They actively incorporate human values in terms of fearlessness, integrity, and commitment to attain excellence. This assumption lead to close relationship of corporate values and organizational agility. European excellence models, in turn, rather focus on continuous improvement, results, and fact-based management. These characteristic traits have also been revealed within the survey regarding organizational agility in terms of resilience and innovativeness. Table 3 shows the demographic proportion of respondents and their job position and job tenure.

Table 3. Structure of respondents by job position and job tenure.

<i>Job Position</i>	<i>Proportional Distribution (frequency)</i>	<i>Job Tenure (average in years)</i>
<i>Executive Manager (disciplinary and/or professional)</i>	48	6 – 10
<i>Employee</i>	138	0 – 5
<i>Total (valid)</i>	186	

The scales for resilience were mainly created on the organizational change management behavior. According to Zwetsloot et al. (2013) related aspirational value factors are adaptivity, organizational mindfulness, collaboration and networking relationships as well as informedness. For the framework of organizational agility, sense making capabilities of the management team (TC) and clearness of vision and values were identified (Baškarada & Koronios, 2018). Innovativeness was measured on the employee level composed of organizational culture dimensions in terms of social support, people involvement and development with its behavioral and cognitive attributes like proactiveness, creativity, or openness (Ruvio et al., 2014; Ali et al., 2017). The following Figure 1 reports the obtained results of the subsequent measurement model analysis.

Figure 1. Results of the measurement model considering factor loadings and Chronbach's Alpha.

Foremost, common research quality indicators are evaluated in order to ensure a meaningful interpretation of data. The content validity of the questionnaire has been examined through a pre-study with experts from industry and academia. After a few amendments, the final questionnaire was prepared to use. Before testing the research question, Chronbach's Alpha has been measured to test and maximize the reliability of the data. All factor loadings have a value greater than 0.45, alpha exceeds the threshold of 0.7 and consequently fulfill the criteria for good internal consistency. Especially, the conceptual framework for the 5S organizational agility construct gained empirical evidence as proposed by Baškarada and Koronios (2018). Furthermore, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was used to evaluate the convergent validity. All the constructs satisfy this criterion since their AVE values are acceptable at 0.5 level.

In a next step, the structural model will be analyzed. First, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is examined to assess the predictive power for organizational agility as the endogenous construct (Cohen, 1988). The model explains 61.2% of the variance in organizational agility with all paths

being significant, indicating a strong support for the research model. The predictive relevance through Stone-Geisser criterion (Q^2) of the model proposed was found by performing blindfolding using the cross-validated redundancy computation. The Q^2 value for organizational agility is 0.272 and thus has above medium predictive relevance. Finally, this study also reports the overall goodness-of-fit measure, the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) to avoid model misspecification. A value less than 0.10 is considered as a suitable level for this indicator (Henseler et al., 2014). The composite model of SRMR analysis produces a value of 0.095, which confirms the overall model fit.

Overall, resilience ($\beta = 0.533$, $p < 0.001$) and innovativeness ($\beta = 0.359$, $p < 0.001$) have significant relationships highlighting their important role with organizational agility. This finding is in line with the theoretical concepts that have been mentioned in the other studies (Lee & Rha, 2016; Braun et al., 2017; Ali et al., 2017). Nonetheless, each of the resilience and innovativeness items play different roles in the formation of organizational agility. Establishing a certain level of confidence and stress-resistance has more effect on organizational agility than fostering innovativeness. This result can be attributed to the biological phenomenon of “survival of the fittest”. In contrast, values of an innovation culture help to spark a deeper passion for the work of agility. It can be observed that vision values serve as motivators to the individual context and form important cross-linkages between these two areas.

Moreover, it will be useful to analyze the core value statements identified from Chapter 4.1 regarding single item approach. All indicators that show perception mean more than 3, are already in the top quartile of the organizational agility stage. After the assessment, the results show the agility level of the industry in question as outlined in Table 4). The average value of all respondents from the automotive industry who regard their corporate culture as being highly vulnerable is 49.63%. This insight is in accordance with the grey-marked low perception mean score of the indicators.

Table 4. Survey perception mean of each indicator.

No.	Item	Mean	Std.dev. (samp.)	Excess Kurtosis	Skewness
1	Adaptivity	2.215	0.960	0.062	0.696
2	Collaboration	3.333	0.937	-0.577	-0.160
3	Creativity	3.066	0.856	-0.192	-0.287
4	Information Sharing	2.710	0.968	-0.384	0.181
5	Involvement	2.663	0.876	-0.348	0.030
6	Mindfulness	2.452	1.016	-0.544	0.365
7	Openness	3.232	1.021	-0.427	-0.143
8	Reward System	2.919	1.057	-0.612	0.025
9	Sharing Vision & Values	2.876	0.904	-0.261	0.072
10	Social Support	3.103	0.879	-0.041	-0.154
11	TC - Searching	3.140	0.934	-0.406	-0.163
12	TC - Seizing	3.301	0.907	-0.286	-0.373
13	TC - Sensing	3.371	0.896	-0.346	-0.262
14	TC - Shaping	3.177	0.998	-0.454	-0.167
15	TC - Shifting	2.892	1.067	-0.645	0.056
16	Proactiveness	3.129	0.895	-0.559	0.060

Collaboration and cooperation are important aspects of everyday work and the employees and managers seem to have the right capabilities within a changing environment. In comparison, the flexible change of corporate structure and implementation of new strategy or business model become partial weaknesses. This assumption can be grounded to the low perception mean score of shared vision and values. All indicators in terms of information sharing, involvement, mindfulness or remuneration are composed of distinctive corporate value statements from Table 2. Especially values like trust, appreciation, or challenge are no shared values and consequently are rather espoused as the normative framework for employees' behavior from the top management. By leveraging these indicators to a higher level, organizations can achieve better results for organizational agility.

Practical implications and limitations

Kotter and Heskett (1992) in corporate culture and performance studies showed that companies with strong adaptive cultures based on shared values outperformed other companies by a significant margin. Drawing from the empirical findings, establishing a culture of "sharing values" becomes a critical factor for decision-making, acting, and on the behavior of people. To make organizations more adaptable, the inherent values must be lived by the employees, but, in fact, core values often remain vague, indefinable, and without normative and behavioral consequences or goals. This, in turn, requires the creation and maintenance of meaningful and rewarding work conditions as employees becoming more and more reflective.

At close scrutiny, the integration of human values into the organization's values will actively incorporate the transformation process towards an agile organization. This proposition is also supported by neuroscience research that states social connectedness as key factor for personal identification with corporate values (Ruff & Fehr, 2014).

This study, no doubt, has some implications for executives who wish to stimulate organizational transformation processes. For organizations within the premium automotive industry it can be proposed to establish three cluster of values, namely ethical values (being) that include trust or interconnectedness, behavioral values (doing) that comprise transparency or responsibility, and aspirational values (becoming) that help to build resilience. Especially for long-established corporations it is recommended to adopt organic core values (e.g., creative, challenging, stimulating) and to overcome mechanistic managerial values (e.g., structured, regulated, closed). Incorporating human values in business excellence models will furthermore improve their effectiveness and sustainability in uncertain times. The main challenge will be to implement the concept of corporate agility as a core value for the automotive industry.

Accordingly, three main propositions will be derived from this study: If human values were more prominent in company value statements, it would be (1) positive related to employees workforce agility, because it helps individuals to unleash their capabilities, (2) for companies, through better organizational success in terms of performance and goal achievement, and (3) possibly for the society generally through a resultant improvement in corporate identity and reputation.

Although this study provides considerable insights, it has certain research limitations. Corporate value statements were particularly investigated within a specific type of industry with a sample dominated by the big three countries with regards to the premium automotive sector: Europe (Germany), the U.S., and China. Therefore, caution should be exercised when generalizing the results and further studies are needed to empirically test the validity of the findings. Also, smaller corporations could be expected to have less obstacles between top management's espoused corporate values and the actual practices.

Conclusion and future scope

By building organizational agility, organizations may be better equipped within today's volatile and ever-changing business environments. The source of organizational agility in the present study context is viewed from two important perspectives of ambidexterity, namely resilience and innovativeness. This research explored the corporate values that are relevant for enhancing organizational agility within the premium automotive industry. The corporate values identified were then grouped in six overarching value clusters that are strongly connected to the construct of organizational agility. Based on the assessment and analysis of the survey, the findings provide some support for the conceptual premise that human values have a significant impact on agile behavior and organizational health. In brief, employees on the individual level should demonstrate values like trust, respect, courage, and openness, whereas creativity, collaboration, and discovery are encouraged organization-wide by everyday routine of transparency, adaptation, and commitment.

The challenge for long-established corporations will be to overcome barriers of "espoused" values, as these values are not lived by the whole corporation, therefore leading to a lower level of organizational agility. Besides the fact that the research field is challenging and dynamic, this paper will help speed progress in this area by highlighting several key issues that need more attention.

Especially the field of social connectedness provides a range of new perspectives, embracing readiness to adopt values and mapping out of values. Future research could study the development of corporate values over a longer period of time and see if external changes affect values and other organizational outcomes, e.g., strategic orientation. This longitudinal study would be more suitable for examining the antecedents and consequences of ambidextrous organizational agility, providing more accurate results. Additionally, future studies could expand the sample to include other sectors of the economy, such as the IT branch, and to conduct group analysis between these different types of industries.

This in-depth study could include the following aspects:

- (1) To assess the relationships between the various clusters of corporate values identified.
- (2) To explore the impact of different organizational culture types on the adoption and internalization of the values that support workforce agility.
- (3) To undertake empirical research on the influence of environmental aspects on organizational identity.

References

- Abbott, G. N., White, F. A., & Charles, M. A. (2005). Linking values and organizational commitment: A correlational and experimental investigation in two organizations. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 78(4), 531–551. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317905x26174>
- Ali, Z., Sun, H., & Ali, M. (2017). The Impact of Managerial and Adaptive Capabilities to Stimulate Organizational Innovation in SMEs: A Complementary PLS–SEM Approach. *Sustainability*, 9(12), 2157. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9122157>
- Appelbaum, S. H., Calla, R., Desautels, D., & Hasan, L. (2017). The challenges of organizational agility (part 1). *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 49(1), 6–14. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ict-05-2016-0027>
- Arthur, D. Little. (2014). *Battle for Sales in the Premium Segment*. Retrieved from https://www.adlittle.com/sites/default/files/viewpoints/AMG_2013_Battle_for_Sales.pdf
- Audi AG. (2019). *2018 Annual Report*. Retrieved from <https://www.audi.com/content/dam/gbp2/en/company/investor-relations/annual-report-2018/audi-annual-report-2018-en.pdf>
- Bardi, A., Lee, J. A., Hofmann-Towfigh, N., & Soutar, G. (2009). The structure of intraindividual value change. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 97(5), 913–929. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0016617>
- Bardt, H. (2017). Autonomous Driving — a Challenge for the Automotive Industry. *Intereconomics*, 52(3), 171–177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10272-017-0668-5>
- Baškarada, S., & Koronios, A. (2018). The 5S organizational agility framework: a dynamic capabilities perspective. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 26(2), 331–342. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijoa-05-2017-1163>
- BMW Group. (2019). BMW Group's unique Corporate Culture. Retrieved April 24, 2019, from <https://www.bmwgroup.jobs/de/en/about-us/corporate-culture.html>
- Braun, T. J., Hayes, B. C., DeMuth, R. L. F., & Taran, O. A. (2017). The Development, Validation, and Practical Application of an Employee Agility and Resilience Measure to Facilitate Organizational Change. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 10(4), 703–723. <https://doi.org/10.1017/iop.2017.79>
- Cadillac. (2019). Mission Statement and Values. Retrieved April 25, 2019, from https://www.capitalcadillac.com/Capital_Mission
- Center of Automotive Management. (2018). *Automotive INNOVATIONS 2018*. Retrieved from http://www.auto-institut.de/index_htm_files/CAM_PM_AutomotiveINNOVATIONS_2018_Marken.pdf
- Charbonnier-Voirin, A. (2011). The development and partial testing of the psychometric properties of a measurement scale of organizational agility. *Management*, 14(2), 119–156. <https://doi.org/10.3917/mana.142.0119>
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. 2nd edn. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Daimler AG. (2019). *Annual Report 2018*. Retrieved from <https://www.daimler.com/documents/investors/reports/annual-report/daimler/daimler-ir-annual-report-2018.pdf>
- De Brentani, U., & Kleinschmidt, E. J. (2004). Corporate Culture and Commitment: Impact on Performance of International New Product Development Programs. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 21(5), 309–333. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0737-6782.2004.00085.x>
- Deloitte Insights. (2018). *2018 Global Human Capital Trends: The rise of the social enterprise*. Retrieved from <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/at/Documents/human-capital/at-2018-deloitte-human-capital-trends.pdf>
- Dempsey, J. (2015). Moral Responsibility, Shared Values, and Corporate Culture. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 25(3), 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.1017/beq.2015.31>
- Felipe, C. M., Roldán, J. L., & Leal-Rodríguez, A. L. (2016). An explanatory and predictive model for organizational agility. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(10), 4624–4631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.04.014>
- Grantham, C., Ware, J. P., & Williamson, C. (2007). *Corporate Agility: A Revolutionary New Model for Competing in a Flat World*. New York, NY: AMACOM.

- Hamel, G. (2012). What matters now. *Strategic Direction*, 28(9).
- Henseler, J., Dijkstra, T. K., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., Diamantopoulos, A., Straub, D. W., ... Calantone, R. J. (2014). Common Beliefs and Reality About PLS: Comments on Rönkkö & Evermann (2013). *Organizational Research Methods*, 17(2), 182–209. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428114526928>
- Illes, K., & Vogell, C. (2018). Corporate values from a personal perspective. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 14(2), 351–367. <https://doi.org/10.1108/srj-07-2017-0114>
- Jaguar Land Rover. (2019). Cultures and Values. Retrieved April 25, 2019, from https://www.jaguarlandrovercareers.com/content/Cultures-and-Values/?locale=en_GB
- Kotter, J. P., & Heskett, J. L. (1992). *Corporate Culture and Performance*. New York, NY: Free Press.
- Lee, S. M., & Rha, J. S. (2016). Ambidextrous supply chain as a dynamic capability: building a resilient supply chain. *Management Decision*, 54(1), 2–23. <https://doi.org/10.1108/md-12-2014-0674>
- Lis, A. M., & Lis, A. (2016). Factors Affecting Group Identity of Cluster Structures. *Journal of Intercultural Management*, 8(2), 125–152. <https://doi.org/10.1515/joim-2016-0013>
- Meyer, P. (2019). Tesla Inc.'s Organizational Culture & Its Characteristics (Analysis). Retrieved April 24, 2019, from <http://panmore.com/tesla-motors-inc-organizational-culture-characteristics-analysis>
- NIO. (2019). Careers. Retrieved April 26, 2019, from <https://www.nio.com/careers>
- Persona GLOBAL. (2018). *Organizational Agility Survey*. Retrieved from <https://www.personaglobal.com/performance-solutions/material-preview/organizational-agility-survey-17-3>
- Porsche AG. (2019). Company Culture and Values. Retrieved April 26, 2019, from <https://www.porsche.com/germany/aboutporsche/jobs/employer/values/>
- Rahman, H. (2014). Organizational Sustainability. *International Journal of Business Intelligence Research*, 5(2), 17–38. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijbir.2014040102>
- Rawlins, B. L. (2008). Measuring the Relationship Between Organizational Transparency and Employee Trust. *Public Relations Journal*, 2(2), 1–21.
- Ruff, C. C., & Fehr, E. (2014). The neurobiology of rewards and values in social decision making. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 15(8), 549–562. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3776>
- Ruvio, A. A., Shoham, A., Vigoda-Gadot, E., & Schwabsky, N. (2014). Organizational Innovativeness: Construct Development and Cross-Cultural Validation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 31(5), 1004–1022. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpim.12141>
- Schein, E. H. (2004). *Organizational Culture and Leadership* (3rd ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Schwartz, S. H., Cieciuch, J., Vecchione, M., Davidov, E., Fischer, R., Beierlein, C., ... Konty, M. (2012). Refining the theory of basic individual values. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 103(4), 663–688. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0029393>
- Sherehiy, B., Karwowski, W., & Layer, J. K. (2007). A review of enterprise agility: Concepts, frameworks, and attributes. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 37(5), 445–460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ergon.2007.01.007>
- Shoham, A., Vigoda-Gadot, E., Ruvio, A., & Schwabsky, N. (2012). Testing an organizational innovativeness integrative model across cultures. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 29(2), 226–240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jengtecman.2012.01.002>
- Talwar, B. (2009). Comparative study of core values of excellence models vis-à-vis human values. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 13(4), 34–46. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13683040911006774>
- Toyota Motor Corporation. (2019). *Annual Report 2018*. Retrieved from https://www.toyota-global.com/pages/contents/investors/ir_library/annual/pdf/2018/annual_report_2018_fie.pdf

- van Rekom, J., van Riel, C. B. M., & Wierenga, B. (2006). A Methodology for Assessing Organizational Core Values. *Journal of Management Studies*, 43(2), 175–201. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2006.00587.x>
- Volvo Group. (2019). Our Values. Retrieved April 25, 2019, from <https://www.volvogroup.com/en-en/about-us/company-values.html>
- Zwetsloot, G. I. J. M., Scheppingen, A. R. van, Bos, E. H., Dijkman, A., & Starren, A. (2013). The Core Values that Support Health, Safety, and Well-being at Work. *Safety and Health at Work*, 4(4), 187–196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2013.10.001>

Acknowledgments

Not applicable.

Funding

Not applicable.

Conflict of Interests

No, there are no conflicting interests.

Open Access

This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. You may view a copy of Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License here: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>